

Size Distribution Report by Intensity

v2.2

Sample Details

Sample Name: new 0.003 2

SOP Name: ZnO NPs_PSD.sop

General Notes:

File Name:	new.dts	Dispersant Name:	DMSO
Record Number:	2	Dispersant RI:	1.470
Material RI:	1.60	Viscosity (cP):	2.0000
Material Absorbtion:	0.100	Measurement Date and Time:	03 May 2023 10:42:06

System

Temperature (°C):	25.0	Duration Used (s):	60
Count Rate (kcps):	299.2	Measurement Position (mm):	4.65
Cell Description:	Disposable sizing cuvette	Attenuator:	11

Results

	Size (d.n...	% Intensity:	St Dev (d.n...
Z-Average (d.nm): 490.4	Peak 1: 502.1	100.0	120.9
Pdl: 0.231	Peak 2: 0.000	0.0	0.000
Intercept: 0.633	Peak 3: 0.000	0.0	0.000

Result quality **Good**

